
Intellectual Property Rights In India: Challenges And Solutions

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Abstract:

Intellectual property rights are the product of the human mind. Countries of the world have been protecting them by making their own laws for centuries. The World Trade Organization was formed in 1995. Agreement on the Trade related aspect of intellectual property rights (TRIPS) or TRIPS is an agreement of this organization. All the countries which are members of the World Trade Organization have to accept it and make their laws accordingly. We are also changing the laws related to intellectual property rights due to this so that they become TRIPS compliant. This is why many people say that we are not changing the laws because we need them but because TRIPS says so and because of the World Trade Organization and TRIPS we have lost our sovereignty. Anyway, this controversy is different. We have to talk about open source software and are only learning a little about intellectual property rights in this regard.

India and America want to take mutual trade to new heights through bilateral relations. But intellectual property rights come in the way. On one hand, while there are some flaws in India's intellectual property rights system, some negativity has also been shown from America's side. But we can understand the dispute, the reason for the dispute and the process of resolving disputes only when we know well about intellectual property rights, so let us first understand what intellectual property rights are?

Keywords: IPR, TRIPS, Industrial Design, Copyright, Patent, Trademark.

Introduction:

A new invention in any field, whether it is a product or a process, is given a patent. But this research should not be purely scientific research, but it should have some industrial value, patents are given on various medicines, mobile phones, cars and other small parts of vehicles. If a company wants to buy such patented research of a researcher and bring it to the market, the value of this patent can be incalculable and in such a case a researcher can literally become a millionaire. An artistic part of an item for industrial use can be protected by the form of intellectual property called industrial design, such as shape, color, and

form. A working part of a car, such as an engine or tire, is protected by a patent, while its shape, color, and size are protected by industrial design. In short, an industrial design mark is given on the aesthetic elements of commercialized items. However, copyright is only on pure works of art. Different types of intellectual property rights grant their creator ownership rights over this creation for a certain period of time. During this period, no one can make this creation without the permission of the creator. Its owner has a monopoly over it during this period. The government of the country grants this monopoly to the creator as a reward for the hard work, money, and

time spent on this creation.

Objectives of Research:

1. To Study of Intellectual Property Rights in India.
2. Reviewing the disputes between India and the US and their resolution

What is an intellectual property rights?

The rights given to individuals in the context of their intellectual creation are called intellectual property rights. In fact, it is believed that if a person creates any kind of intellectual creation (such as creation of a literary work, research, invention etc.), then first of all, that person should have exclusive rights over it. Since this right is given only for intellectual creation, hence it is called intellectual property rights.

Intellectual property means morally and commercially valuable intellectual creation. Grant of intellectual property rights should not be taken to mean that the creator of a particular intellectual creation will have the right over it forever. It is necessary to mention here that intellectual property rights are given in view of a fixed time period and a specified geographical area.

The basic purpose of granting intellectual property rights is to encourage human intellectual creativity. Since the scope of intellectual property rights is wide, it was considered necessary that corresponding rights and related rules etc. should be arranged for a particular area. On this basis these rights can be classified into the following forms

- 1) Copyright
- 2) Patent
- 3) Trademark
- 4) Industrial design
- 5) Geographical indication

Flaws in India's Intellectual Property Rights System:

Many people believe that the flaws in India's Intellectual Property Rights system

are responsible for the lack of expected progress in India-US trade. Although there is not much truth in this, but still we have a suitable opportunity to see how India's Intellectual Property Rights system.

The Indian Patent and Design Act were first made in India in the year 1911. Again after independence, the Patent Act was made in 1970 and it was implemented from the year 1972. Amendments were made in this Act by the Patent (Amendment) Act, 2002 and the Patent (Amendment) Act, 2005. From the year 2005, India started giving patents on medicines as well. The administration of the patent system in India is under the 'Controller General of Patents, Designs, Trademarks and Geographical Indications'. The headquarters of the Indian Patent Office is in Kolkata. The participation of private sector in research and development in India is very low and the main reason for this is India's weak intellectual property rights system. In the year 2005, when amendments were made in the Indian Patent Act in accordance with the expectations of the World Trade Organization, more than 56,000 applications for patents were pending before the Controller General of Patents, Designs, Trademarks and Geographical Indications.

Exactly 10 years later, i.e. in the year 2015, 2,50,000 applications for patents and 5,00,000 applications for trademarks were pending. As soon as we look at these figures, at first glance it appears that India's intellectual property rights system is in a sick state.

What should be the way forward?

The Industrial Development Organization of the United Nations has proved through a study that the countries which have a well-organized intellectual property rights system have seen rapid economic development. Hence, there is an urgent need for reform here.

India should make the 'Controller General of Patents, Designs, Trademarks

and Geographical Indications' efficient and proper. The pendency of a large number of applications shows that our system of granting patent rights should be improved and hearing of applications within a certain time should be made mandatory.

It should be noted that the Government of India has started the exercise of reforming the intellectual property rights system and has determined that the time limit for hearing the applications for obtaining patent rights will be 1 month and this is definitely a welcome step.

Disputes between India and America and their solutions:

America has often been pressuring India to make its intellectual property rights rules consistent with the intellectual property rights of the US and the European Union. America has many times expressed its concern by accusing the provisions of Indian intellectual property rights rules on issues like counterfeiting, piracy and medicines of weakness. America has also been warning India many times that it can bring India to the lower level in the category of "Primary Foreign Country" and on this basis some restrictions can also be imposed on India.

In view of the above circumstances, while on the one hand India has moved forward towards the formulation of its national intellectual property policy, on the other hand, India has also got a clean chit from the World Trade Organization in the matter of intellectual property disputes raised by America. It is known that the World Trade Organization has created the TRIPS system to resolve trade disputes related to intellectual property rights. The agreement related to TRIPS i.e. 'Trade Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights' was made in the Uruguay Round of 1986-94.

It is worth mentioning that some trade groups had raised their voice against India that India has issued some compulsory

licenses for manufacturing patented medicines. But in the review report of the World Trade Organization, it was found that in March 2012, India had issued the first and only compulsory license which was related to cancer medicine. Thus, the Government of India is not only emphasizing on rationalizing its rules related to intellectual property rights but it is also keeping in mind the public interest. Apart from this, the government has also been making necessary amendments in its rules giving importance to global activities.

Conclusion:

As far as the Indo-US dispute is concerned, it is important for India to 'balance patent laws with health considerations 'to control the prices of medicines. In many countries, the prices of medicines are high. But life-saving medicines should be within the reach of common citizens at a reasonable price.

This is the reason why the Indian government did not succumb to the pressure of the US and other western countries demanding amendments in the patent law. As far as the relative trade is concerned, India has been balancing its health concerns and patent laws till now and the judiciary has also played an important role in this.

It is known that in the year 2005, the rewash a sudden short age of cancer medicines in the market and when the matter was investigated, it was found that a company named Novartis had dragged other drug manufacturing companies to court because the company claimed that it alone had the right to sell this medicine in India.

It is worth mentioning that in 2005, Swiss company Novartis applied for a patent on an anti-cancer drug called Gleevec, which was rejected by the Indian Patent Office. Against this decision, Novartis had approached the Supreme Court. However, the Supreme Court rejected Novartis' petition.

India is a developing country and its emerging market is beneficial for other countries. It is worth mentioning that patents are beneficial for the profits of big companies. Therefore, we should register a large number of patents like China and relax it to the optimum level so that research and inventions are not limited to only a few hands.

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